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**The main directions of socio-economic
development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions**

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
JIZZAKH BRANCH OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN
NAMED AFTER MIRZO ULUGBEK

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The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific
and practical conference on the topic

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(Part 2)

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The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan: problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific and practical conference on the topic – Jizzahk: Department of economics and tourism of Jizzakh branch of the national university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, December 6, 2024, 450 pp.

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

INNOVATSION TADBIRKORLIK VA INNOVATSION KOMPANIYALAR UCHUN RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonda innovatsion va texnologik tadbirkorlik - uning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, muammolari va istiqbollari ko'rib chiqiladi. O'zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan innovatsion loyihalarning asosiy yo'nalishlarining qisqacha tavsifi berilgan. Innovatsion tadbirkorlikni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar sarhisob qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiyalar, innovatsion tadbirkorlik, infratuzilma, institutsional to'siqlar, innovatsion rivojlanish indeksi.

Samarali menejmentni joriy etish bo'yicha jahon va mahalliy tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, aynan innovatsion tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish alohida korxonalar va umuman davlatning iqtisodiy o'sishining ishonchli asosi hisoblanadi. Ammo, afsuski, inqiroz hodisalarining namoyon bo'lishi an'anaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda jiddiy muammolarga va uning faoliyati samaradorligining pasayishiga olib keladi. Shu sababli, umuman tadbirkorlik faoliyati samaradorligini oshiradigan boshqaruvning yangi usullarini izlashning obyektiv ehtiyoji paydo bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, aynan innovatsion tadbirkorlik zamonaviy iqtisodiy rivojlanish omili sifatida yangi jamiyat rivojlanishining ustuvor elementiga aylanishi kerak.

Bugungi kunda milliy iqtisodiyotning o'sishi ko'p jihatdan bozor munosabatlari subyektlarining innovatsion rivojlanish darajasi bilan belgilanadi, ularning tadbirkorlik faoliyatida dinamik imkoniyatlar va eng yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanish, iste'molchilar ehtiyojlarini qondirish yo'llarini ijodiy aniqlash, mahsulotlarni takomillashtirish va yangilash, ularning bozordagi mavqeini mustahkamlash va biznes samaradorligini ta'minlash, ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlari bilan belgilanadi. Ya'ni, zamonaviy korxonalar faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, innovatsiyalar ularning rivojlanishi samaradorligining endogen omiliga aylandi. Tegishli tendensiyalar dinamik tashqi muhit faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda innovatsiyalarga asoslangan zamonaviy korxonalar rivojlanishini ta'minlash uchun nazariy va uslubiy yondashuvlar va amaliy asoslarni ishlab chiqish zarurligini dolzarblashtiradi.

Xullas, hududlarda innovatsion tadbirkorlikka eng ko'p ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar qatoriga davlatning demokratik jarayonlarga aralashuvi, investorlar uchun imtiyozli shart-sharoitlar yaratilishi, korrupsiya kiradi. Demak, innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sir darajasi bo'yicha birinchi o'rinda tashqi iqtisodiy sanksiyalar, ikkinchi o'rinda korrupsiya, uchinchi o'rinda esa siyosiy vaziyat turadi. Ushbu uchta omil bir-biri bilan bog'liq bo'lib, O'zbekistonni xalqaro hamjamiyatda yetarli darajada barqaror bo'lmagan siyosiy va iqtisodiy mamlakat sifatida tavsiflaydi.

Navbatdagi eng muhim omil – innovatsion tadbirkorlar uchun imtiyozli shart-sharoitlar yaratishdir. Imtiyozli ish rejimlari amalda ko'pincha muayyan korxonalar uchun davlat subsidiyalari shakli va mahalliy manfaatlarni amalga oshirish vositasi sifatida qo'llaniladi. Maxsus zonalar doirasida innovatsion loyihalarga sarmoya kiritish uchun imtiyozlar berish amaliyotida qo'llaniladi. Ko'pincha, faol innovatsion faoliyat bilan shug'ullanadigan muayyan korxonalar yoki tarmoqlar uchun maxsus soliqqa tortish tartibi imtiyoz sifatida qo'llaniladi, masalan, qo'shilgan qiymat solig'i olinadi, lekin ishlab chiqaruvchilar ixtiyorida qoladi. Aynan shu jihatlar O'zbekiston hududlarida innovatsion tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish uchun asosiy to'siqlar bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Ushbu omillardan kelib chiqqan holda, innovatsion tadbirkorlar uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratishning mohiyatini aniqlash mumkin, bu esa ijobiy va raqobatbardosh innovatsion muhitni yaratishga, shuningdek, innovatsion infratuzilmani qo'llab-quvvatlash va rivojlantirishga qaratilgan innovatsion jarayonlarga xizmat ko'rsatishga o'tish zaruratidan iborat.

Shunday qilib, O'zbekistonda dunyoning boshqa rivojlangan mamlakatlari bilan solishtirganda ilm-fan intensivligi va fan unumdorligi yetarli darajada yuqori baholanmagan, ammo so'nggi yillarda yuqori texnologiyali tarmoqlardagi vaziyat yaxshilanmoqda, bu tegishli ko'rsatkichlardan dalolat beradi.

2022-yilning 29-sentyabr kuni "Global innovatsiyalar" indeksining 2022-yilgi hisoboti e'lon qilindi. O'zbekiston Global innovatsion indeksda O'zbekiston 2015-yilda 141 ta davlat orasidan 122-o'rinni egallagan bo'lsa, 2022-yilda 131 ta davlat orasida 40 pog'onaga yuqorilab, 82-o'rinni egalladi hamda Markaziy Osiyoning yetakchisiga aylandi va Markaziy va Janubiy Osiyo mamalakatlari orasida Hindiston va Erondan keyin 3-o'rinni egalladi. Ushbu natijaga erishishda so'ngi yillarda mamlakatimizda ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar sohasida olib borilayotgan keng ko'lamli islohotlar hamda Davlatimiz rahbarining soha rivojiga alohida e'tibor qarganlari alohida e'tiborga sazovor.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Dobni C. B., Wilson G. A., Klassen M. [Business practices of highly innovative Japanese firms](#) // Asia Pacific Management Review. – 2021. – p. 101-108. – doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2021.06.005.
2. Andreev V.I. Menejerning o'zini o'zi rivojlantirishi / V.I. Andreev. - M.: Delo, 2014. – 275 b.

3. Bleyk R.R., Mouton D.S. Boshqarishning ilmiy usullari / R.R., Bleyk, D.S. Mouton [trans. ingliz tilidan I. Yushchenko]. – Kiev: Oliy maktab, 2013. – 274 p.
4. Белокур О.С., Цветкова Г.С. [Технологическое предпринимательство как фактор инновационного развития провинциального региона](#) // Экономические отношения. – 2019. – № 3. – с. 2213-2228. – doi: 10.18334/eo.9.3.40918 .
5. Климентьева А.Ю. [Создание условий органами местного самоуправления для развития инновационного предпринимательства](#) // Экономика, предпринимательство и право. – 2018. – № 4. – с. 213-222. – doi: 10.18334/epp.8.3.39656 .